

POLITICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF DATA ON GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE AND WOMEN'S PARTICIPATION IN ELECTED OFFICE IN TIJUANA AND MEXICALI

Alma Beatriz Navarro Cerda

senior research professor

Martin Cutberto Vera Martinez

senior research professor

Abstract

This paper analyzes data on women's participation in politics and violence against women in Tijuana and Mexicali, as well as contextual elements from Baja California. Tijuana and Mexicali are used as case studies. The paper hypothesizes that "even though women have held elected office, this has not had an impact on reducing indicators of violence against women." It also broadly reviews the institutional policies implemented to reduce the gender gap through women's participation in public decision-making. While, in political terms from a democratic perspective, we can infer that this is considered an element for the consolidation of this model, in pragmatic terms for society, it has not been reflected in facts that can be demonstrated by concrete data.

Keywords: Democracy, women's political participation, reduction of violence against women.

Introduction

The fight for gender equality has been a rocky road with great challenges, of which it can be said that from the emergence of peaceful and non-peaceful demonstrations by women to make their voices heard, in the old world of the last century, they were the turning point that gave rise to a period of social recognition of women in decision-making regarding who might be suitable to govern, of which we must not forget that even in some places considered liberal democracies they did not have the right to property or employment in the last century.

The greatest leaps forward came when women gained the right to participate in elections, but only with the right to vote, not to be elected, as that prerogative was reserved solely for the male gender. Even during this period, in some countries with totalitarian tendencies, if someone was caught engaging in any practice contrary to traditional reproduction, it was considered a serious crime and consequently severely punished. Therefore, there was little chance that women would ever have the rights that are basic in many countries today, much less be considered eligible for political office, which may have seemed incongruous and absurd at the time.

The construction of the new American world, emphasized the need to consider the role of women in political processes, but before political rights were expected civil rights would be a reality where private property was the main need for the citizen and a utopia for women in the 19th century and early 20th century [given that most countries] did not have the legal right to property, even in parliamentary governments.

Currently, the scenarios for women have changed for the benefit of this gender, however, that does not mean that the ideals of equity that are sought have been achieved, but the great strides have represented great challenges in the design and implementation of policies, since parallel to these achievements, there is still an extremely important element and that is the cultural aspect, which, like the "Deep State", is so rooted in social groups that a radical change will not be possible

when dictating and implementing a social policy for gender equity, but under the incrementalist scheme, the structures will have to be changed step by step with the objective of achieving balances that allow the full development of all genders, if it is in the interest of said governments and societies.

Thus, while this paper aims to explain the 21st-century phenomenon of the impact of elected women in decision-making positions, it uses a comparative case study between the cities of Tijuana and Mexicali. Therefore, it hypothesizes that "even though women have held elected office, this has not had an impact on the reduction of indicators of violence against women." In other words, having more women in the public administration system does not imply that conditions for women are improving, and that these changes are reflected in positive changes reflected in terms of impact. While this is considered a somewhat pessimistic scenario, the truth is that, in order to give these new women a vote of confidence, we must remember that they arrived in an administrative system designed by men. On the other hand, it is recognized that there is pressure from the international context to position women in elected office, a phenomenon that responds to the United Nations resolution of 2011, which specifically states the following: "Women continue to be largely marginalized from the political sphere throughout the world, often as a result of discriminatory laws, practices, attitudes and gender stereotypes, low levels of education, lack of access to health care services, and because poverty affects them disproportionately."

While some United Nations member countries have decades of experience with women in politics, for the vast majority, it is still part of the pending agenda. For Mexico, it has also been a complicated task; however, it is now evident that the role of women in politics is increasingly active and they are increasingly present in impactful decision-making.

Basic Ideas about Democracy

The concept of democracy has been considered one of the most important for the construction of the

Liberal State; however, this has not meant that democracy is the same for all nation-states in the world, especially for those that have not adopted any type of democratic trait. However, in the strictest sense, a democracy is a regime where structures have been designed so that all those who wish to participate within the system can participate, giving the opportunity for this participation to be a choice and not an imposition (Morlino, 1995).

It is for this reason that the quality of democracy is currently being debated, which has been measured solely through quantitative electoral aspects, that is, a democratic system is of quality if the greatest possible number of voters participated in an electoral process x (Morlino, 2005). However, our opinion differs with regard to the idea of quality, since if an element of quality is going to be attributed to something like "democracy", this analysis should be accompanied by other elements that have no relation to the size of the electorate and its participation in the elections, but rather with deontological reasons, about the expectations that a democratic model must meet. Therefore we suggest thinking that to decide if a regime is democratic with quality it should be covered by good results in the quality of life indicators and not be distracted by merely political issues, it is not denied that it may be a reason for a political issue to potentiate a scenario at a certain given time, but why deceive ourselves intellectually if we know that democracy is not good for eating, that is, Why should we give our trust to a person who does not know us to make decisions about our lives and define rules for our lives as citizens and non-citizens? Another necessary question is if this person is not looking for our good in community why should we trust them? These are the questions that should be asked when questioning about the quality of democracy, For what reason? Although the individual of the twentieth and twenty-first centuries has not had much opportunity to generate great changes in the systems, they have been born, grown and have adapted to the different systems previously established and designed by past generations, however the approach is that democracy remains the same, but we must advance in expectations For democracy, knowing how many people voted in an election won't help us feed our families. What will be useful is for those who are elected to govern who meet expectations by creating the socioeconomic conditions for a

better life. One of the best arguments for not transitioning to authoritarian regimes is that democracy would lead a better life. In this sense, we mean that individuals must have the opportunity to develop under equal conditions, and that these conditions cannot be temporary for political reasons, but must be part of the institutional model, which includes a gender perspective.

Therefore, our methodology considers security as one of the indicators of quality of life. This study specifically analyzes the gender-based violence index. It is hypothesized that increased female participation in elected office is not necessarily reflected in a decrease in indicators of violence against women. Data from Tijuana and Mexicali are used as case studies: the former because it is a secondary city in the state of Baja California, with the geographic implications of this status, and the latter because it is the state's capital. Another common characteristic is that both cities are border cities. Finally, inferences are drawn about their relationship with the violence indicators.

The first step is to understand the contextual aspects for Baja California, which is why the main data for the state and for each of the two cities, Tijuana and Mexicali, are presented below.

Socioeconomic contextual aspects in Baja California: Emphasis on Tijuana and Mexicali

One of the widespread beliefs in Mexico is that the northern region is believed to have better conditions in all aspects of the population's socioeconomic life. Although, in terms of job opportunities along the Baja California border, there are many employment opportunities in the maquila and service industries, there are still gaps in the supply of good opportunities and also inequality of opportunity for men and women. According to data obtained by the National Institute of Statistics, Geography, and Information in 2020, there were 3,769,020 people residing in Baja California, 49.6% women and 50.4% men. The median age in the state is 30 years. Of every 100 pesos contributed to the Baja California economy, 60.92 are from tertiary activities, 36.02 from secondary activities, and 3.06 from primary activities. Although the percentage of men in Baja California is higher than the total population, this section will examine the extent to which women have participated in activities related to the community's economic, political, and social development.

Table 1

Comparison by gender of five-year labor contribution.

Entity federal	Five-year age group	2005			2010			2020		
		Total	Men	Women	Total	Men	Women	Total	Men	Women
Baja California	Total	2,844,469	1,431,789	1,412,680	3,155,070	1,591,610	1,563,460	3,769,020	1,900,589	1,868,431

Prepared by the authors using data from INEGI.

In Tijuana, the population according to INEGI data in 2020 was 1,922,523 inhabitants, while in Mexicali it was 1,049,792 inhabitants in the same year. Of these, the population is distributed as follows: 953,783 females and 968,740 males in Tijuana, while in Mexicali the population is 520,544 females and 529,248 males. To date, current President Sheinbaum is considering conducting a new population census, so the results are expected in the following months or by 2026.

Regarding economic activity, Tijuana, being one of the most important border cities in the world, and especially in Baja California, is characterized by a unique dynamism and a high-impact development capacity. By 2024, it registered exports of \$39.952 billion USD, with a presence in the medical, automotive, and transportation sectors, in general across a wide range of the manufacturing sector. Regarding international trade, in May of this year 2025, it registered international purchases of US\$2.944 billion, and international sales of US\$3.246 billion, according to data from the Mexican Ministry of Economy. Regarding its exports, the United States was its main destination, registering US\$32.882 billion in 2024, where monitors and projectors that do not incorporate television reception devices were the main exported product (Ibid.).

Meanwhile, in the city of Mexicali, despite being the capital, its economic activity is not as agile and dynamic as its sister city across the border, Tijuana. Official data from the Ministry of Economy of the Mexican

federal government show that for 2024, it registered a total of US\$11.653 billion in exports, with the United States as the main destination and integrated electronic circuits as the main product. Meanwhile, imports for 2024 amounted to US\$7.579 billion, again with the United States as the main origin and integrated electronic circuits as the main product. However, other products are imported, such as valves, air pumps, electrical wires and cables, plastic items, among others.

One of the advantages of geographic location is precisely the ability to share products, which allows for the creation of other types of links such as cultural and social ones. This has been demonstrated in different border areas as well as in northern Mexico with the United States, sharing culture which includes problems of crime incidence, although this work only addresses the issue for Tijuana and Mexicali, cities in the federal entity of Baja California, Mexico.

Some political background in Mexico

In Mexico, the history of women's political participation has been documented since Carmen Serdán's 1910 participation during Francisco I. Madero's anti-re-election campaign. Hermila Galindo was later singled out in 1918 as one of the key figures who promoted women's political rights. The following table shows some of the most relevant data regarding women's political participation in this country.

Table 2

Background of women's political participation in Mexico.

Year	Event
1918	Hermilia Galindo petitioned the 1916-1917 Constituent Congress to recognize women's political rights (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1922-1924	Elvia Carrillo, the first candidate elected to the Yucatán Congress, served only two years in office (Alejandre Ramírez and Torres Alonso, 2016).
1922-1924	In Yucatán, women were allowed to vote in local and state elections (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1924-25	In San Luis Potosí, a law was passed allowing literate women to participate in the municipal elections of 1924 and the state elections of 1924 (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1934	The Mexican Women's Front was formed, and the leader of the National Revolutionary Party called for the formation of the party's Women's Sector. Its first leader was Edelmira Rojas, widow of Escudero (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1935	Lázaro Cárdenas transformed the Women's Sector into a Women's Action Office, dependent on the National Executive Committee. Its first director was Margarita Robles, with whom she founded the United Front for Women's Rights, which fought for the right to vote, the expansion of literacy programs, daycare centers, maternity wards, and hospitals, and brought women into the political struggle. Its leaders included Consuelo Uranga, Frida Kahlo, Adelina Zendejas, and María del Refugio García (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1936	In Puebla, Article 33 of the local Electoral Law was amended, recognizing that "men and women of Puebla are voters and therefore have the right to be registered on the electoral roll" (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).

1936	The Inter-American Women's Committee for Democracy is consolidated (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1937	Lázaro Cárdenas sends the initiative to reform Article 34 of the Constitution to the Senate as a first step toward women obtaining citizenship. The initiative failed (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1938	The United Front, founded in 1935, launches an intense campaign to reform Article 4 of the Constitution to recognize women's political rights. The movement finds support in 21 states, but not in the Congress of the Union (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010)
1941	The national women's alliance, which called for women's access to public office, was highlighted. As a result of this movement, Matilde Rodríguez was appointed head of department and Palma Guillen was appointed Mexican ambassador to Colombia (Ramos Escandón, 1994).
1946	The Congress of the Union approved the initiative submitted by President Miguel Alemán, adding Article 115 to the Constitution to establish that women would participate in municipal elections on equal terms with men, with the right to vote and be elected. The reform went into effect on February 12 of the following year (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1947	María del Carmen Marín del Campo became the first female mayor of Aguascalientes (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1953	In an ordinary session of the Chamber of Deputies, Articles 34 and 115, Section I, of the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States were declared amended to establish that: "Citizens of the Republic are men and women who, being Mexican, also meet the following requirements: be at least 18 years of age if married, or 21 if unmarried, and have an honest livelihood" (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1953	The right of women to vote and to be voted for is recognized. (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1954	Aurora Jiménez de Palacios, First Federal Deputy for District I of the State of Baja California. (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1955	Women go to the polls, for the first time nationwide, to elect federal deputies to the 43rd Legislature (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1958	Macrina Rabadán becomes the first federal deputy from an opposition party—the Popular Socialist Party—to represent the State of Guerrero in the 44th Legislature (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1967	Alicia Arellano Tapia and María Lavallo Urbina became the first two female senators of the Republic, representing Sonora and Campeche, respectively, in the 46th and 47th Legislatures. Lavallo Urbina later became President of the Senate (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1971	The feminist organization Women in Solidarity Action (MAS) is born. This is the first in a series of feminist groups influenced by American and European feminism after 1966. Since then, feminism has championed the phrase "the personal is political" (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1975	International Women's Day is established by the UN and is celebrated every March 8 (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1979	Griselda Álvarez Ponce de León becomes the first female Governor of Mexico for the State of Colima. (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1980	The National Program for the Integration of Women into Development is created, dependent on CONAPO (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).

1985	The National Women's Commission is created, attached to the Ministry of the Interior (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1993,	Approval of the gender quota (Article 115 of the Federal Code of Electoral Institutions and Procedures). (Electoral Institute of the State of Sinaloa, 2007).
1997	Candidacies for deputies or senators must not exceed 70% for the same gender (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1988	Ifigenia Martínez Hernández becomes the first senator from an opposition party, as part of the 54th Legislature (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1993	Reform to COFIPE requires parties to nominate more women for elected office (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1993	Approval of the gender quota (art. 115 of the Federal Code of Electoral Institutions and Procedures).
1996	The Government of Mexico creates the National Women's Program (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
1997	Candidacies for deputies or senators should not exceed 70% for the same gender (Reynoso, D., & D'Angelo, N, 2006).
2000	The Mexiquense Women's Institute is created (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
En 2002	Political parties must register at least 30% of their candidates for elected office as women; additionally, on multi-member lists, one woman for every three men (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
El 2 de agosto de 2006	The General Law on Equality between Men and Women was published, which aims to guarantee equal opportunities and treatment between men and women (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
2007	The General Law on Women's Access to a Life Free from Violence (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010) was enacted.
2019	A series of constitutional reforms were approved to achieve parity in all three branches and levels of government, as well as autonomous bodies (Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145, 2010).
2020-2021	In the largest electoral process by number of elected positions, women won more than six governorships, and parity was achieved in the Chamber of Deputies (50/50) and in almost all local governments (National Electoral Institute, 2022).

Source: Prepared by the authors using third-party information.

Women's participation in Baja California politics: electoral processes

In Baja California, the State Electoral Institute (IFE) has existed since 1994, serving as the autonomous state body for organizing local elections. The following tables show historical information from the 1995-1998 municipal elections in Tijuana and Mexicali. For the Tijuana data, it is noteworthy that during the first terms of government, women's participation in elected office was 30.76%, the same as in Mexicali. During the 1998-2001 period, women represented 13.33% in Tijuana, while in Mexicali it remained at 30.76%. In the 2001-2004 period, women represented

14.28% and 30.76% in Mexicali. In the following period, from 2004-2007, women represented 21.42% in Tijuana and 23.07% in Mexicali. In the 2007-2010 period for both cities it was 30.76%; in the 2010-2013 period it was 54.54% for Tijuana and 88.88% for Mexicali; in the 2013-2016 period for Tijuana and Mexicali it was 41.66%; in the following period from 2016-2019 it was 70% for Tijuana and 88.88% for Mexicali; in the 2019-2021 period it was 88.88% for Tijuana and Mexicali, and the same will be true for the 2021-2024 period.

Below is a list of women in current public administrations by municipality of Tijuana and Mexicali.

Table 3.

Historical distribution of positions by gender in Tijuana

Tijuana	Relative majority										Representation Proportional		Total	
	P	S	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	M	H	M	H
1995-1998	H	H	H	H	H	M	H	H	H	H	3	4	4	13
1998-2001	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	2	5	2	15
2001-2004	H	H	H	H	M	M	H	H	H	H	0	6	2	14
2004-2007	H	H	H	H	H	M	H	H	H	H	2	5	3	14
2007-2010	H	H	H	H	H	M	H	M	H	H	2	5	4	13
2010-2013	H	M	H	H	H	H	H	M	H	M	3	4	6	11
2013-2016	H	H	H	H	H	M	H	H	M	M	2	5	5	12
2016-2019	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	2	5	7	10
2019-2021	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	3	4	8	9
2021-2024	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	3	4	8	9
Totales	1	3	1	2	2	7	1	4	2	4	27	22	47	120

Source: Baja California State Electoral Institute (2021). Where R1, R2, ... R8, mean councilor number one and so on.

Table 4

History of the distribution of positions by gender in Mexicali

Mexicali	Relative majority										Representation Proportional		Total	
	P	S	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7	R8	M	H	M	H
1995-1998	H	H	M	H	M	H	H	H	M	H	1	6	4	13
1998-2001	H	H	H	M	H	H	H	H	H	H	3	4	4	13
2001-2004	H	H	H	M	H	H	H	H	M	H	2	5	4	13
2004-2007	H	H	H	H	H	H	H	M	H	H	3	4	4	13
2007-2010	H	H	M	H	M	H	H	H	H	M	1	6	4	13
2010-2013	H	H	M	M	H	M	H	H	H	H	5	2	8	9
2013-2016	H	H	M	H	H	H	M	H	M	H	2	5	5	12
2016-2019	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	3	4	8	9
2019-2021	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	3	4	8	9
2021-2024	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	M	H	3	4	8	9
Totales	2	1	6	4	4	2	3	2	5	2	31	26	44	113

Source: Baja California State Electoral Institute (2021). Where R1, R2, ... R8, mean councilor number one and so on.

As can be seen, in these municipalities there has been a clear increase in women's participation in elected office, which speaks to the importance and relevance attributed to the national policy of gender equality and political participation. However, it is notable that, in the initial periods in the city of Mexicali, the participation rate remained at four women compared to 13 men. Subsequently, with structural changes in Mexico's electoral legislation, the number of representatives per city council decreased. Although a mandatory quota for women's participation was increased, gender inequality persisted. A similar situation occurred in Tijuana, but they did not achieve the same level of equality in participation as in the city of Mexicali. In this sense, it is important to recognize that women's participation in elected office has been increasing in both cities. What we need to know is whether this has had a positive impact on the reduction of rates of violence against women in these cities, which is reviewed in the following sections.

Institutional policies implemented to reduce the gender gap

The gender issue continues to be one of the issues within government agendas, so we can find programs that have been designed and implemented at the national level with local impact to seek to reduce the gap between women and men, in such a way that the United Nations has developed a program to train public policy makers in gender matters, said program is an international cohort and is called "Programs with a gender perspective. Training for their development and implementation", and is focused on institutions developing skills that allow the design and implementation of plans, programs and initiatives to address violence against women and girls (Spotlight Initiative, 2021), which has been adopted by different organizations.

Another element to consider is the implementation of policies aimed at designing public budgets in Mexico, which should be prepared with a gender perspective. This is intended to ensure that expenditures across the entire federal public administration achieve equality between men and women in public spending (UN Women, 2018).

During the administration of the federal government in Mexico under the current President Sheinbaum, the "Comprehensive Program to Prevent, Address, Punish, and Eradicate Violence against Women" (PIPASEVM 2021-2024) was launched. This program responds to one of the objectives of the National Development Plan (PND 2019-2024) of the previous term. It is coordinated through the Ministry of the Interior, the Undersecretary of Human Rights, Population, and Migration, and the National Commission for the Prevention and Eradication of Violence against Women (CONAVIM), with the goal of eradicating violence against women.

Another program designed for the same purpose is the "Support for Women's Institutions in the Federal Entities" (PAIMEF) and the Support Program for Specialized Shelters for Women Victims of Gender Violence, their Daughters and Sons (Milenio, 2025). It is also worth remembering that the current administration eliminated women's institutions to create the Secretariat of Women. However, the background on this issue is the General Law on Women's Access to a Life Free of Violence, which was approved in 2007 (Ramírez, 2021). In this sense, for more than 10 years, the issue of eradicating gender violence has been operating with a different structure and approach. The following section analyzes data for Tijuana and Mexicali in relation to the different types of gender violence experienced in both border cities.

Indicators of violence against women: Analysis of Tijuana and Mexicali

Mexicali and Tijuana are cities that belong to the State of Baja California, one of the 32 entities of the Mexican Federation. As mentioned in previous paragraphs, these cities share the northern border with the United States; however, they have significant differences in terms of size and level of socioeconomic development. However, regarding the issue of violence, there are similarities due to the increase and decrease in both cities. The following tables, presented with official data from the Secretariat of Citizen Security of the State of Baja California, compare Tijuana and Mexicali.

Table 5.

Comparison between Mexicali and Tijuana in data on the incidence of domestic violence.

	Mexicali	Tijuana	Percentage difference
Year	Domestic violence	Domestic violence	
2015	2695	5076	88.34%
2016	2322	4540	95.52%
2017	2452	4567	86.25%
2018	3121	4823	54.53%
2019	3443	4910	42.6%

Prepared by the authors using data from INEGI (2021).

Table four shows data on domestic violence cases handled. Proportionally, there is a difference of more than 80% between Tijuana and Mexicali. However, as of September 30, 2025, according to data from the Baja California State Attorney General's Office, 10,488 cases of domestic violence were reported throughout

the state, of which 3,121 were in Tijuana and 4,185 in the city of Mexicali. Proportionally, this means that there is more domestic violence in the city of Mexicali, representing 0.40% of the total, while in Tijuana it is 0.17%.

Table 6.

Comparison of Mexicali and Tijuana in data on the incidence of Sexual Abuse.

	Mexicali	Tijuana	Percentage difference
Year	Sexual abuse	Sexual abuse	
2015	278	609	119.06
2016	289	586	102.76
2017	263	556	111.4
2018	344	607	76.45
2019	385	630	63.63

Prepared by the authors using data from INEGI (2021).

Regarding the crime of sexual abuse, as can be seen, there is a significant difference between the two cities, and contrary to expectations, the rate has not de-

creased but has remained slightly on the rise. As of September 30, 2025, 1,169 cases were recorded throughout the state of Baja California.

Table 7.

Comparison of Mexicali and Tijuana in data on the incidence of Femicide.

	Mexicali	Tijuana	Percentage difference
Year	Femicide	Femicide	
2015	3	4	33.33%
2016	2	6	200%
2017	2	5	150%
2018	6	11	83.33%
2019	5	13	160%

Prepared by the authors using data from INEGI (2021).

Regarding the crime of femicide, as can be seen, the data more than doubled in the city of Tijuana between 2015 and 2019, and the same occurred in Mexicali between 2015 and 2018. According to the latest re-

port from the Attorney General's Office as of September 30, 2025, 33 cases of femicide were recorded across the state, which proportionally represents 21.22 in each municipality.

Table 8.

Comparison of Mexicali and Tijuana in data on other sexual crimes.

	Mexicali	Tijuana	Percentage difference
Year	Other crimes that violate sexual freedom and security	Other crimes that violate sexual freedom and security	
2015	71	177	149.29%
2016	86	127	47.67%
2017	74	146	97.29%
2018	70	149	112.85%
2019	80	139	73.75%

Prepared by the authors using data from INEGI (2021).

Due to the diversity of the problem, classifications of other crimes that violate sexual freedom and security are used, which include various types of sexual assault not classified under the main violation, such as sexual abuse, sexual harassment, statutory rape, and corruption of minors (CPEB, 1989). From these data it can be observed that only in 2016 there was a significant decrease, while in 2015, 2017, and 2018 the data were very high and proportionally the city of Tijuana doubled the numbers. This scenario has not improved since in the last report from August 2025, 1,045 were registered in the city of Tijuana and 917 in the city of Mexicali, this means that from 2015 to 2025 there was a percentage increase for Tijuana of 490.39%, while for the city of Mexicali, 1,191.54%.

Conclusions

One of the State's main objectives is to guarantee the well-being of its population. This reasoning, in principle, must be interpreted through deontological considerations that have been cemented in the construction of the State through the social contract and primarily during the implementation of government models based on liberal principles. In this sense, the State generally acquired more regulatory obligations, which means that, although it yielded to private participation in the economy, this had a domino effect that impacted the regulation of social life and the government's administrative apparatus. Thus, in democratic governments, de facto powers have played a fundamental role in seeking balances in relation to the capacity to provide

services and care for their population. In this work, the gender issue was explored, with the hypothesis that even though women have held elected office, this has not had an impact on the reduction of indicators of violence against women, taking Tijuana and Mexicali in Baja California, Mexico, as a case study. Therefore, according to official data, it is verified, since two things could be inferred, first, in the city of Mexicali, there are more cases of violence against women and also greater participation of women in elected office, therefore, the fact that there are women in power does not mean a positive impact through the reduction of cases of violence. On the other hand, in the municipality of Tijuana, fewer cases of women's participation in politics were recorded, as well as fewer cases of violence against women. Another fact worth highlighting is that violence against women is proportionally more prevalent in the municipality of Mexicali than in Tijuana, even though Tijuana has almost twice the population of Mexicali. On the other hand, good practices in social support programs seeking to mitigate this problem have been observed; however, the results have been insufficient, given that both cities have shown a significant increase in violence against women. Therefore, questions remain about what measures should be implemented to combat this problem and other cultural and social actions should be considered.

References

1. Alejandro Ramírez, G. L., & Torres Alonso, E. (2016). The First Feminist Congress of Yucatán 1916. The Road to Suffrage Legislation and Recognition of Citizenship for Women. *Construction and Stumbles. Political Studies (Mexico)*, (39), 59-89.
2. Penal Code for the State of Baja California. (1989) Available at <https://transparencia.pjbc.gob.mx/documentos/pdfs/Codigos/CodigoPenal.pdf> Accessed October 14, 2025
3. Congress of the Union. (2007). General Law on Women's Access to a Life Free of Violence. Official Gazette of the Federation.
4. DECREE amending Articles 2, 4, 35, 41, 52, 53, 56, 94, and 115; of the Political Constitution of the United Mexican States, regarding Gender Parity. (2019). Published in the Official Gazette of the Federation on June 6, 2019.
5. Electoral Institute of the State of Sinaloa. (2007). From gender quotas to a constitutional mandate at the federal level. Electoral Institute of the State of Sinaloa.
6. National Electoral Institute. (2022). Diagnosis. The scope and results of parity. Federal and Local Electoral Processes 2017-2018 and 2020-2021. National Electoral Institute.
7. National Institute of Statistics and Geography (INEGI, 2021). National Survey on the Dynamics of Household Relationships (ENDIREH). Available at: https://www.inegi.org.mx/contenidos/programas/endireh/2021/doc/endireh2021_presentacion_ejecutiva.pdf
8. Law on Equal Treatment and Opportunities between Women and Men of the State of Mexico, Decree No. 145 (State of Mexico, Mexico). Published in the Official Gazette of the Government of the State of Mexico on September 6, 2010. (pp. 6)
9. Morlino, L. (1995). Democracies in Pasquino, G. Manual of Political Science. Alianza.
10. Morlino, L. (2005). Quality of Democracy: Notes for Discussion. *Metapolitics: A Clean Look at Politics*, 9(39), 37-53.
11. Ramirez, J. et al. (2021). Gender Violence in Latin America: Strategies for its Prevention and Eradication. *Journal of Social Sciences*. University of Zulia.
12. Ramos Escandón, C. (1994). Women's Political Participation in Mexico: From Rifles to Votes, 1915-1955. Metropolitan Autonomous University of Mexico (pp. 165).
13. Reynoso, D., & D'Angelo, N. (2006). Quota Laws and Their Impact on the Election of Women in Mexico. *Politics and Government*, XIII(2), 279-313.
14. Sosenski, Susana, & Sosenski, Gregorio. (2010). In Defense of Children and Women: An Approach to the Life of Psychiatrist Mathilde Rodríguez Cabo. *Mental Health*, 33(1), 1-10. Retrieved October 14, 2025, from http://www.scielo.org.mx/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0185-33252010000100001&lng=es&tlng=es.
15. <https://www.milenio.com/politica/paridad-y-violencia-politica-de-genero-que-es-y-como-hacer-frente>
16. <https://www.elciudadano.com/derechos-humanos/naciones-donde-mujeres-no-tienen-derechos-humanos/07/01/>
17. <https://lac.unwomen.org/es/que-hacemos/liderazgo-y-participacion-politica>
18. <https://www.milenio.com/politica/programas-prevencion-violencia-mujeres-sin-reglas-operacion>
19. <https://www.opmsinaloa.org.mx/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/Cronologia-de-los-Derechos-Electorales-y-Civiles-de-las-Mexicanas.pdf>
20. Gender Violence in Latin America: Strategies for its Prevention and eradication
21. Sociodemographic Overview of Baja California 2020